

HRI Framework for Continual Learning in Face Recognition

Giulia Belgiovine*^{1,3} and Jonas Gonzalez-Billandon*⁴, Alessandra Sciutti¹, Giulio Sandini², Francesco Rea²

Abstract—Recognizing human partners is an essential social skill for building personalized and long-term human-robot interactions. However, robots deployed in complex, real-world environments have to face several challenges, such as managing unstructured interactions with multiple users, limited computational resources, and intrinsic and continuous variability of their sensory evidence. To cope with these challenges, we propose a framework to perform autonomous incremental learning for open-set face recognition suitable for unconstrained HRI scenarios. We validated the proposed framework in a real-world experiment, demonstrating its suitability to let the robot autonomously interact with multiple people while creating a labeled database of their faces across various encounters. Furthermore, we evaluated how an off-the-shelf model performed with data gathered from the HRI setting and proposed a fine-tuned model obtained with a transfer learning technique. Analyses about automatic threshold determination and rehearsal methods for memory sampling were also proposed. Our preliminary results suggest that exploiting the first-hand robot’s experience could be crucial to ensure better models’ performance and, therefore, could be advantageous for the acceptance and effectiveness of social robots in the long run. With this work, we aim to provide insights on continual learning approaches in the HRI field to promote autonomous and personalized solutions meaningful for real-world applications.

I. INTRODUCTION

Robots are increasingly designed to enter complex social contexts where they will interact closely with multiple people for extended periods. The complexity and variability of these scenarios require the robot to learn advanced social skills autonomously and incrementally, possibly drawing on its first-hand experience as an embodied agent that inhabits and interacts directly with the world. Indeed, learning during deployment rather than the design phase is crucial for the next generation of social robots that aspire to achieve autonomy and adaptation, ensuring engaging and personalized interactions with humans, even in the long term.

The first and fundamental step toward this goal is to learn to recognize people previously met and to identify those who have never been encountered before (i.e., open-set recognition). In the latter case, the new user may need to be added in memory for the recognition in subsequent meets (i.e., open-world recognition). This is the case when a new student is introduced to a robot teacher or a new patient is introduced to a robotic therapy. In such applications, the intermediary and the end-users are often non-experts in

robotics, so it would be ideal for this process to be handled as autonomously as possible by the robot [1]. This implies the ability to identify the users and to store autonomously in a structured way the sensory data (e.g., voices and faces) associated with them. Ideally, the system should allow not only the incremental learning of new identities but also the updating of new evidence for already known classes (e.g., recognizing a previously seen user after a new haircut). In other words, a known user can be initially mistaken for another, but these variations can be learned over time and combined with other modalities to improve recognition, similar to what humans do.

The aspects that need to be considered to make learning in HRI effective are various such as (i) possible unstructured multiparty contexts, (ii) limited computational resources and availability of data, and (iii) continuous variability of robots sensory evidence. Regarding the complexity of dynamic interactions with groups, one should consider that people interacting with the robot may change their position in space, leave the interaction, or the robot’s field of view. In such highly unconstrained situations, the robot must maintain a sense of what is happening in the environment. The attentional and reasoning mechanisms guiding its behavior should allow natural interaction with users as well as the efficient organization of its first-hand sensory experience to personalize future interactions. Currently, most HRI studies focus on one-to-one interactions. However, research and technological challenges brought by handling multiparty interactions are utterly different from dyadic ones and should be addressed to demonstrate the applicability and worth of social robots in real-world contexts [2].

Another significant challenge is to cope with limited computational resources, low-resolution sensors, and noisy data. Moreover, data gathered from HRI are generally very different from benchmark datasets used to build off-the-shelf models. This explains why when applying these solutions to robotic platforms, there is generally a drop in performance. To address this limitation and exploit the full potential of deep learning algorithms (which reached state-of-the-art results in this field), we should take advantage of robots’ ability to collect and label their own training data as the basis for context exploration and comprehension.

The last aspect to consider is that robots have to learn over subsequent interactions, using a continuous stream of observations rather than a predefined “batch” of evidence. Thus, Continuous Learning (CL) lends itself as a practical approach for robots that need to learn autonomously over time and incrementally develop a set of complex skills and knowledge [3]. The concept of learning continually from experience has

*authors contributed equally for this paper

¹ Cognitive Architecture for Collaborative Technologies lab, Italian Institute of Technology, Genova, Italy

² Robotics Brain and Cognitive Science lab, Italian Institute of Technology, Genova, Italy

³ Università degli Studi di Genova, Genova, Italy

⁴ Huawei Noah’s Ark Lab, Paris, France

been present in artificial intelligence and robotics since their birth [4]. However, despite the method’s suitability for this field, studies implementing a continual learning approach are still few, mainly because of technological and experimental constraints introduced by robots. Most still rely on static datasets, simulation environments, or offline evaluation of the models. Testing state-of-the-art algorithms in robotics systems and possibly unconstrained interactions is essential to overcome these limitations.

This study proposes a robotic architecture for autonomous incremental learning for open-set face recognition. The framework allows managing the user recognition pipeline almost autonomously in unconstrained HRI scenarios. We validated our framework in an ecological user study over 9 days, showing that the proposed solution can cope with the challenges generally encountered in HRI and discussed above. We compared an off-the-shelf face recognition model with a fine-tuned one obtained using transfer learning. Finally, we tested various rehearsal CL approaches to limit the use of memory, which is essential for robotics applications. Our final goal is to provide insights on CL approaches for autonomous long-term personalization in HRI, bridging the gap between machine learning and robotics. In this way, we enable robots to exploit their own experience efficiently, avoiding the problem of human annotations of the dataset, reducing the bias introduced by off-the-shelf models trained on different benchmark datasets [5], and improving the model robustness as the number of interactions increases.

A. Research Questions

In the present work, we aim to answer the following research questions: **i)** Is our architecture suitable for real-world face recognition problems, in unconstrained multiparty HRI (i.e., able to successfully manage the automatic creation of a multimodal dataset suitable for learning)? **ii)** How do off-the-shelf models perform in HRI applications? How can we address the drop in performances induced by the difference in the data used for training such networks? **iii)** How can rehearsal techniques for continual learning be useful in HRI scenarios? How do those techniques perform in terms of accuracy for open-set recognition?

II. RELATED WORK

A. Robotic Frameworks for Multiparty HRI

Several works have attempted to provide solutions for social robots to identify and interact with multiple users during free interactions. Examples are robots developed to entertain large audiences in museums or shopping malls. For instance, in [6], the authors developed a socially intelligent robot designed to interact with the general public in open spaces by integrating methods from audiovisual scene processing, social-signal processing, and conversational AI. However, these studies generally focus on short-term interactions, so they do not address the problem of autonomously managing the user recognition pipeline (meant as an open-set problem) to support long-term personalization.

In a less recent study, Aryananda et al. [7] used the Mertz robot in a public environment to autonomously create a dataset of faces with 500 subjects during an unstructured interaction thanks to an architecture consisting of a perceptual, attention, and behavior system. Although this was one of the first works to address incremental and autonomous user recognition in HRI, the system required initial training to recognize users, and the robot did not show proactive behavior to correctly label the acquired data, resulting in a very noisy dataset. In [8], the authors highlight the need for a framework able to model and flexibly represent humans for HRI applications. They propose a prototype pipeline that could be implemented to acquire social signals in real-time, including the processing of face and voice for person recognition management. However, the proposed framework is not yet fully deployed or evaluated online in a real HRI scenario.

B. Face Recognition in HRI

Face recognition has been studied in the past decade exhaustively in the context of security systems reaching significant progress [9]. However, most proposed approaches have not been tested on HRI scenarios.

Today the preferred approaches for face recognition are based on deep convolutional neural networks, which reached state-of-the-art results, overcoming to a significant extent different issues related to uncontrolled factors, such as partial occlusions and non-frontal pose [10]. However, those results are usually achieved on static and curated datasets and in verification or closed-set identification problems, where it is assumed that the users to be recognized are already present in the dataset. These assumptions make it difficult to understand how these solutions perform online in real-world HRI. Several works applied deep networks for face recognition in HRI settings. For example, Churamani et al. [11] used it to personalize the interaction with the robot NICO. Prescott et al. [12] implemented a multimodal memory system for the iCub humanoid to demonstrate its ability to recognize faces. Wang et al., [13], proposed a multiple face re-identification system based on face embeddings and unsupervised clustering. However, the final goal of integrating the system into a robot remains further work. In [14], the authors present a multimodal method to improve biometric verification. They merge facial and voice information and propose a sampling method of the input data to increase intra-class variability.

In most of these works, the main focus was either on the development of face recognition methods (not addressing challenging HRI scenarios and leaving the experimental setup as simplified as possible) or on the development of computational frameworks (in this case, with less attention on the learning part). We think it is important to advance and promote the intersection of Machine Learning and robotic communities to assess both the computational architecture aspect, which allows the robot to behave in unstructured scenarios autonomously, and the learning dimension for developing long-term autonomous solutions suitable to real-world applications.

C. Continual Learning in Robotics

A definition of Continual Learning (CL) is algorithms that, given a potentially unlimited stream of data, should learn from a sequence of partial experiences where all data is not available at once, as opposed to a non-continual learning setting where all data are available as a preset batch of data and can be processed as desired [3]. This approach to the learning process fits perfectly with the field of robotics, where the agent has to learn from a continuous stream of data, which in our specific case are people’s faces. CL algorithms face many problems such as imbalanced or scarce data, catastrophic forgetting, or data distribution shifts.

CL algorithms can be divided into three main approaches: i) Dynamic architecture, ii) Regularization, and iii) Rehearsal approaches. In this paper, we focused on the rehearsal approaches coupled with a deep metric learning model. This was motivated by both the advantages of deep learning models for face recognition, which can deal efficiently with open-set setup, and by the simplicity and the effectiveness of rehearsal approaches to deal with CL tasks. Recently, Prabhu & al. proposed the GDumb method, which greedily stores samples in memory as they come and, at test time, trains a model from scratch using samples in the memory [15]. We decided to test this relatively simple but effective approach in our context and also proposed a variation to sample the data with fixed memory. When working with robots, it is desirable to pay attention to memory management; this is why we investigated a low data regime that could be easily stored in the robotic system.

III. ARCHITECTURE

Intending to propose a modular architecture, we integrated stand-alone modules with the YARP middleware [16], allowing for easy modification to match the needs of the interaction. We used the humanoid robot iCub as the robotic platform.

Fig. 1. Representation of the computational architecture. Raw data from the iCub robot’s sensors are passed on to perceptual and reasoning mechanisms that, along with the working memory system, allow the robot to interact with users and organize its direct experience, ultimately resulting in the creation of a structured dataset of people’s faces.

A. Audio-Visual Perception

The audio-visual perceptual modules had the task of sensing people, helping the robot to maintain a representation of what was happening around it. This required several audio-visual algorithms to detect, track, and re-identify people.

1) *Sound Localization (SL)*: For the sound localization, we used a Convolutional Neural Network, taking as input the binaural signals from the 2 microphones embedded on the iCub head [17]. The model was used to discern the incoming direction of auditory signals (*left, center, right*) and to turn the robot’s attention towards the sound source.

2) *Face Detector (FD)*: For visual tracking and identification, we first detected the person using a deep learning-based face detection system developed for the iCub robot and described in detail in [18]. We chose this algorithm as it was robust to challenging scenarios such as detecting faces in different orientations, long distances, and sub-optimal lighting conditions.

3) *Multiple Object Tracker (MOT)*: To address interaction scenarios with several people at once, we integrated a Multiple Object Tracker (MOT) into the architecture. It was used to maintain a consistent identity between faces detected in adjacent frames and to let the robot follow the interactive partners if they moved in the space. The tracker algorithm was based on the combination of a Kalman Filter and Hungarian algorithm, allowing to reach an accuracy comparable to state-of-the-art online trackers, but with real-time performance, which is crucial for robotic applications [19]. We used the MOT module to associate each participant interacting with the robot with a unique tracker id T , which was maintained throughout the interaction.

B. Working Memory

In order to share and centralize the representation of knowledge, each module should have access to the same database, and the knowledge contained should follow a standardized format. We called this shared database of knowledge the working memory, the default means of communication among modules. The working memory module consisted of an online yarp-based database called Objects Properties Collector (OPC) [20], used to collect properties of any objects of interest and capable of running in real-time. This module helped the robot retain temporary information useful for achieving its goal of recognizing people and engaging with them. Indeed, for each person detected, a unique item was created in the database and associated with the tracker id created by the MOT. The OPC also contained and updated other properties such as the user’s *name*, and whether the user was *verified*, and *active*. All these proprieties were important to guide the robot’s behavior during the interaction and will be explained in detail in Section IV.

C. Dialog System

In many real-world interaction scenarios, speech is the most used communication channel between a robot and a human. Hence, we integrated into the architecture the open-source Google’s state-of-the-art speech recognizer, which is

fast, accurate, and available for many languages. The speech recognition was integrated with a VAD (Voice Activity Detector), which enabled the processing of voice input only if a minimum threshold in the power of the incoming audio signal was met, computed after a calibration process that took into account the background noise of the environment and the robot’s fan. This process allowed avoiding unnecessary computation of speech recognition. Furthermore, to enable iCub to autonomously sustain a chat-styled, open-domain social dialogue naturally and engagingly, we integrated into our architecture a Natural Language Processing module (NLP). We used the RASA open source conversational AI [21], which is composed of natural language understanding (Rasa NLU) and dialogue management (RasaCore) systems. We trained our conversational agent to ask users for general personal information (to enroll them in the database) or to propose different services (if it already knew them).

D. Face Recognition (FR)

The face recognition module used a triplet-loss trained deep network to compute online euclidean embeddings of detected faces and associate them with a known identity in the gallery or classify them as unknowns [22]. The advantage of this approach is the possibility of identifying previously unseen people using similarity or distance measures. The module then sent information about the person’s identity to the working memory, making it available for other modules. The module also compared embeddings from new detected faces in the scene with embeddings of specific people according to its prior beliefs to perform identity reassignment during the same interaction, as explained in more detail in section IV-B.2.

E. Long-term Memory

During the interactions, the architecture stored the consistent multisensory data (faces and voices) associated with each user. Moreover, thanks to the interactive conversation, the robot could obtain the true label for the gathered data and autonomously organize them in a permanent structured dataset \mathcal{D} . This represented the equivalent of the robot’s “long-term” memory because the binding process of multisensory evidence was replicated, and the duplex was consistently stored in memory. The person recognition pipeline could be performed without the need for human annotations, which constitutes a key advantage of the proposed solution.

For each participant P_i , the module stored automatically the images of the faces I_i retrieved through the face detector and MOT, together with the audio files of their voice A_i retrieved through an Audio Recorder module ($\mathcal{D} : \{P_i : [(I_1; \dots; I_n)] \cup [A_1; \dots; A_m]\}$).

F. Actions

To track the faces and orient the head of the robot toward the localized speaker, we used the iKinGazeCtrl module: a controller for the iCub gaze capable of steering the neck and the eyes independently [23]. Actions modules also included body motion and facial expression controllers.

G. Interaction Supervisor

The interaction management system was responsible for controlling or communicating with every other module to enable interaction. This module represented a state machine that managed the various behaviors of the robot by sending specific commands to the others modules based on a series of inputs and events. This allowed high modularity since only the interaction management needed to be reprogrammed to achieve a particular interaction.

IV. EXPERIMENT

A. Participants

The experiment was conducted with the support of 26 healthy participants that voluntarily agreed to participate in the data collection (12 males, 14 females, 27.7 ± 2.7 years of age). The entire data collection took place over 9 days. Interactions unfolded in groups of two or three people, each time coming back in random combinations of these groups.

B. Setup and Protocol

The robot was placed in a room where participants, who were researchers or students, were free to come by. In the first phase of the interaction, iCub’s goal was to recognize users and, if necessary, enroll them in the database. After that, if they wanted to keep interacting with it, the robot could help them by presenting the canteen menu or the bookings for lab resources (starting the “lab-assistant” dialogue flow).

1) *Users recognition and enrollment in the database:* For each detected person, a tracker with a unique id was added to the OPC and associated with the FR output, which could be either *unknown* or a *name* from the existing database. Before the robot proactively interacted with the users to correct or confirm its guess on their identity, the property *verified* was set to *false*. The conversational module managed the dialogue flow with the unverified users according to their initial label. While the recognition and verification phase with a single user unfolded, the robot started to save voice and face samples while creating online the corresponding embeddings. Interestingly, at the stage of enrollment in the database, the robot also asked for user’s age and nationality, adding this information to the dataset, such that our model in the future could also rely on this information to strengthen the confidence of predictions.

After this phase, users were marked as *verified* in the OPC and their names were updated accordingly. The associated data (faces and voices) were stored in the robot’s permanent memory with the correct label, without the need for humans intervention.

As long as there were unverified users, the robot performed the above interaction to enroll them in the database. After all people in the scene were verified, the robot started the “lab-assistant” dialogue flow, and only when the intention to terminate the conversation was detected (through the NLU), it ended the current interaction and switched back to attention and recognition mode.

2) *Re-identification system*: In order to cope with very unstructured settings and dynamic interactions, it was necessary to provide the robot with additional skills. For example, it could happen that a user interacting with the robot (marked as *active* in the OPC because actively involved in the interaction) wanted/needed to move in space while talking. In this case, the robot followed the person with its gaze, losing the other participants from its field of view. To deal with such cases, the robot checked each tracker’s status before permanently deleting it from the working memory (for example, a verified user was assumed to be still present in the scene but not active in the interaction at that moment). Thus, when the robot framed a “new” face during the interaction (i.e., one not been present in its field of view for some time), it leveraged its prior knowledge and compared the similarity between the embedding of that face and those of the people who were participating in the interaction, i.e., the verified but inactive users. If the computed embedding did not match any of these users, then a new prediction was made, considering the whole gallery. In this way, it could optimize the identity reassignment process.

V. DATA ANALYSIS

A. Data Processing and Models

We processed each face sample according to the standard face alignment procedure presented in [22], obtaining as final probes the ones shown in Fig. 2, with an average size of 40x40 pixels. We chose the Deep Learning Network Facenet [22] trained on the CASIA benchmark dataset [24] as the baseline algorithm. The model learns a mapping from face images to a compact Euclidean space, where distances directly correspond to a measure of face similarity. Once the model computes the feature embeddings, it is possible to perform face recognition using a distance-based classifier. We used the KNN algorithm to find the closest embedding in the dataset with respect to a query one, and then we used a threshold to accept or reject the match, resulting in a known or unknown classification. The choice of the threshold is essential to ensure a good balance between accuracy in correctly recognizing known people and rejection of unknown ones. In an effort to make the process fully automated, we explored two viable methods taken from the literature to infer the threshold to use on day d , given the gallery obtained on days up to $d - 1$.

We first explored a grid-search approach, dividing the available gallery into a training set and a validation set and using some classes as unknown probes. Then, we chose the threshold among a set of values ranging from 0.4 to 1.5 as the one representing the best compromise between DIR and FAR.

Then we investigated a statistical approach, where the threshold was computed from the positive (i.e., same class) embeddings’ distances distribution according to the formula:

$$thr = \mu_{dist.positive} + 2 * \sigma_{dist.positive} \quad (1)$$

We first investigated how the baseline model performed on our collected data against the fine-tuned model obtained using a transfer learning technique. We retrained the network’s last layer to avoid over-fitting and kept all other layers frozen. This also had the advantage of lowering the training time and the computational cost, allowing it to be run on the CPU.

Fig. 2. Examples of collected faces of different participants (P_i) in the robot database on different days (D_i). The database was characterized by high variability in users’ appearance and environmental conditions.

B. Open-Set Recognition Metrics

The standard metrics for open-set identification are Detection and Identification Rate (DIR) and False Alarm Rate (FAR) [25]. DIR is the fraction of correctly classified samples within the probes of the enrolled users in the test set. FAR is the fraction of incorrectly classified samples within the probes of unknown users in the test set. In other words, DIR metrics increments when the current probe belongs to a previously enrolled user and is identified correctly, while FAR serves as a false positive for unknown users (that is, the probe belongs to an unknown user, but he/she is identified as an enrolled one). Depending on the biometric application, the cost of incorrectly identifying a new user as known may be very different from the cost of incorrectly identifying an enrolled user [26]. For surveillance systems, FAR is more important than DIR. However, in HRI interactions, correctly identifying a known person could be considered more important to promote trust and acceptance toward the robot in the long run. To validate our models, we calculated the FAR and DIR metrics by considering as a test set the data collected on the current day d (downsampled to ensure class balance) and using the embeddings in the gallery collected from day 0 to day $d - 1$. For the online experiment, we used the baseline model.

C. Sampling Memory

Since paying attention to memory management is desirable in robotics, we decided to explore different rehearsal-based CL techniques to gain insight into preferable methods for HRI contexts.

We decided to take a fixed size of samples ($k = 100$) for the memory allocated to each class, and we evaluated two sampling modalities: 1) Random Sampling (RS): this simple but effective approach was proposed recently by Prabhu & al. [15] (GDumb) and consisted in greedily storing k samples in

memory for each class and retraining a new model based on those batches; 2) Time-weighted Sampling (TS): we propose a variant of the previous method, which is more human-inspired and in which the samples k are sampled according to a proportion that depends on the time elapsed since the last interaction. Specifically, given a set of days $\mathcal{D} = [1, \dots, N]$, where N is the latest batch acquired by the robot, we define the number of samples s to be sampled from day D_i as:

$$s = \frac{i}{\sum_{i=1}^N e_i * i} * k \quad e_i = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if interaction at } D_i \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

With this method, we make sure to keep a set of samples to represent each interaction day (to ensure intra-class variability), but we give a higher weight (and thus a higher proportion of samples) to the most recent days.

VI. RESULTS

A. Database Creation

Using our proposed architecture, we successfully created a dataset of visual and auditory data during unstructured multiparty interactions. In 9 days, the robot autonomously collected data from 26 users for a total of 16921 face samples (in addition to audio samples, information about age, nationality, and other general info). During the experiment, we encountered some technical problems for one group interaction in which the MOT module did not work, and therefore, we discarded those data. The final dataset contained 16267 faces. The details of the face database are shown in Table I.

TABLE I
DETAILS OF THE COLLECTED DATASET USING OUR PROPOSED ARCHITECTURE

Day	# Class		# Samples	
	Known	Unknown	Known	Unknown
10/01	0	7	0	694
11/01	4	11	241	1270
12/01	11	2	1888	600
13/01	14	1	3367	102
14/01	13	1	1686	48
17/01	8	1	1281	44
18/01	16	1	2755	178
19/01	12	1	974	45
21/01	11	1	1034	60

Figure 2 shows some face samples collected from the robot’s camera. Notably, each user class presented high variability in terms of face orientation, lighting condition, and appearance, which was valuable for encoding maximal information about a person’s identity, but challenging for recognition. Moreover, people wore masks and sometimes even different ones. As an example, consider the participant in the bottom row of Fig. 2, who changed her appearance considerably from the first interaction day to the following ones as she no longer wore glasses, she had a different mask and a new hairstyle. The low resolution of the images, together with the variability in appearance and environmental

conditions, are intrinsic factors that naturally arise when it comes to HRI applications. Moreover, as it can be seen from Table I, having left the participants free to interact with the robot when/as they wished, the resulting dataset was characterized by high variability in the number of classes per day, frequency of a class appearance, and the number of samples for each of them. All these factors represented a good example of real-world scenarios to test the robustness of Machine Learning algorithms.

Fig. 3. DIR (left panels) and FAR (right panels) computed taking all the gallery and with two different thresholding methods: grid-search (top panels) and statistic approach (bottom panels).

B. Face Recognition Models Evaluation

We first used a grid-search thresholding method and computed the DIR and FAR metrics shown in Fig. 3, top row. From day 4 on, our model outperformed the baseline one, reaching up to 97.7% DIR value on the last day (+11% with respect to the baseline). This could sometimes be at the expense of slightly higher FAR values, which nevertheless remain acceptable given the particular application area.

Then we computed DIR and FAR using the statistical threshold method, and we observed that this approach was not suitable for the baseline model. Indeed, using a threshold based on the distribution of distances, we obtained DIR and FAR values of 0 and 100%, respectively (see Fig. 3, bottom row). This was not the case for the fine-tuned model. Indeed, although the performance during the first day was very low, then the model reached much higher accuracies in terms of both DIR and FAR, up to 97% and 0%, respectively.

To investigate this effect, we plotted the distributions of the positive (same classes) and negative (different classes) distances between embeddings produced by the two models (see Fig. 4). As a demonstrative example, we showed the distributions of distances of the models on day 0, day 2, and day 4 for both the training and the test set. Clearly, the baseline model produced features that were not discriminative enough, as the positive and negative distributions significantly overlap. The fine-tuned model, on the other

Fig. 4. Distribution of positive (same classes, in blue) and negative (different classes, in red) euclidean distances using embeddings produced with baseline (left) and the retrained model (right). We computed it for the different training (top row) and testing (bottom row) dataset.

hand, after the first day in which the number of samples in the database was quite limited, counterbalanced this effect resulting in a clear separation between the two distributions.

C. Rehearsal-based Approaches

As expected, retraining the model resulted in better learning of features; however, this will not scale for prolonged interaction as it will require a consequent amount of memory storage and an increase in training time. Therefore, we decided to evaluate the models by sampling the training dataset according to the two approaches described in Sect. V-C, and using a grid-search threshold method. Comparing the two rehearsal approaches, we can see that no one method distinctly outperformed the other. This was probably due to the fact that the period of interaction in our experiment was limited to 9 days. However, for the retrained model, the Time-weighted Sampling method (TS) reached slightly better performance (Fig. 5), achieving a DIR of 97% versus the 95% of the Random Sampling (RS) method and versus the 81% and 78% of RS and TS baseline, respectively. FAR values were higher for the retrained model (remaining around or below 15%); however, they stabilized around 0% toward the last days.

Fig. 5. DIR and FAR values obtained with the baseline (in blue) and retrained (in red) models using Random Sampling (RS, dashed lines) and Time-weighted Sampling (TS, solid lines) approaches.

VII. DISCUSSION

This study proposes a framework to address the challenging task of continual learning in open-set face recognition, testing it in an unconstrained HRI scenario. To this aim, we developed a computational architecture that allowed the robot to deal with multiparty interactions and successfully organize its experience in a structured multimodal dataset of people met across several days, without the need for human labeling.

Then, we used this dataset to perform preliminary evaluations of deep-learning methods for face recognition in HRI. We investigated two methods to automatically find a suitable threshold and tested different rehearsal-based CL techniques to optimize memory management.

By comparing the baseline model to the fine-tuned one (obtained by a transfer learning technique), we observed, as expected, that the retrained model performed better as the number of interactions with users increased. In contrast, in the first days, the limited samples and low variability characterizing each class caused the fine-tuned model to be more unstable in its performance (especially for those cases in which users changed their look from one day to the next).

The difference in performance can also be explained by the very different nature of data on which the baseline model has been trained (high resolution, good illumination, frontal pose) compared to our dataset. Due to the unconstrained environments in which we collected the data, the images had substantial variations in terms of illumination, resolution, and presence of external factors (facial masks, glasses). The distribution of embeddings distances gave us insight that the baseline model struggled in distinguishing people (i.e., learning good embeddings) and that by retraining the model, we could counteract this effect resulting in more disjoint distributions. Consequently, when using a fine-tuned model, a statistical approach can be used to choose the optimal threshold, relaxing the need to fine-tune this hyperparameter (in contrast, this method was not suitable for the baseline model). To fit into practical robotic applications, we imposed a fixed amount of memory storage as a constraint.

In continual learning, this is known as rehearsal techniques, where the goal is to store a fraction of samples that will be used for learning. Following the results of Prabhu & al. [15], we first chose a random sampling approach for its simplicity and effectiveness. By applying it, we got better results for the retrained model for the DIR values, sometimes at the expense of higher values for the FAR. We also tested an approach that we called Time Sampling, where the data sampled per user was weighted by their oldness. The idea was that old samples should still be considered but not given the same importance as recently gathered ones. Compared to the random sampling approach, results were not much different, probably because of the relatively limited period of time of our experiment.

Although further work is needed to investigate more thoroughly how to improve the generalisability and robustness of the models when dealing with limited and noisy HRI data (especially in the early days of interaction), we should consider that the agent's ability to interact proactively was crucial in mitigating these limitations. Indeed, the ability of the robot to ask for the identity of users and to behave appropriately in case of incorrect predictions compensated for the low performance of the model in the first days, making it more acceptable to users.

Overall, the results suggest that incremental learning with memory optimization is the way forward in robotics, especially for long-term autonomous interactions. Indeed, to deal with the drop in performances of SOTA algorithms, letting robots learn by exploiting their incremental, first-hand sensory experience is essential if we want to take full advantage of the advance in the Machine Learning community. Using simple transfer learning and continual learning approaches, the model learned over time to produce increasingly discriminative features for face recognition. Moreover, assessing those algorithms in such unconstrained experimental scenarios is essential to go toward more autonomous robots. Finally, as a future development of this work, we would like to investigate how multimodal fusion with voice embeddings and soft biometrics data collected by our architecture can boost models' performance.

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